

LIST OF CERAMBYCIDAE AND DISTENIIDAE WHICH HAVE BEEN RECORDED NORTH AND SOUTH OR VERY CLOSE TO GUATEMALA

José MONZÓN-SIERRA¹, Richard W. ZACK² & Larry BEZARK³

¹ Centro de Estudios Ambientales y Biodiversidad. Universidad del Valle de Guatemala, Guatemala

² M.T. James Entomological Collection, Department of Entomology, Washington State University

³ 521 46th Street, Sacramento, California, U.S.A.

We present a list of 128 Cerambycidae and 2 Disteniidae (Coleoptera) which have a distribution known from a country north and south of Guatemala, or only in Belize. It is very possible that this species will eventually be found in Guatemala with more collecting efforts. Most of the information is based primarily on Bezark (2016).

Subfamily PRIONINAE Latreille, 1804

1- *Elateropsis fellerae* (Chemsak, 1983). [BEL]

Subfamily LEPTURINAE Latreille, 1804

2- *Megachoriolaus nigricollis* Chemsak & Linsley, 1974. [MEX, NIC]

3- *Strangalia brachialis* (Bates, 1885) [MEX, BEL]

4- *Strangalia elegans* Giesbert, 1997. [MEX, HON, CR]

Subfamily CERAMBYCINAE Latreille, 1802

5- *Ameriphoderes yucateca* (Bates, 1892). [MEX, HON]

6- *Amphelictus bicolor* Chemsak & Linsley, 1964. [MEX, NIC, CR, PAN]

7- *Anatinomma insulare* Chemsak & Linsley, 1964. [MEX, HON]

8- *Ancylocera sallei* Buquet, 1857. [MEX, CR]

9- *Aneflomorpha giesberti* Chemsak & Linsley, 1975. [MEX, HON, NIC]

10- *Anelaphus debilis* (LeConte, 1854). [USA, MEX, HON]

11- *Anelaphus erici* Santos-Silva, 2021. [MEX, NIC]

12- *Anelaphus eximius* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, HON]

13- *Anopliomorpha gracilis* Chemsak & Chemsak, 1993. [MEX, GUA, HON]

14- *Anopliomorpha hirsuta* (Linsley, 1935). [MEX, HON, NIC, CR, SA]

15- *Asynapteron glabriolum* (Bates, 1872). [MEX, HON, NIC, CR, PAN, SA]

16- *Ceralocyna cribricollis* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, NIC, CR]

17- *Cicatrishphaerion belizense* Bezark & Lingafelter, 2022. [BEL]

18- *Coeloxestia curoei* Eya & Chemsak, 2005. [MEX, HON, NIC, CR, PAN]

19- *Crioprosopus nieti* Chevrolat, 1857. [MEX, CR]

20- *Crioprosopus saundersii* White, 1853. [MEX, HON, NIC]

21- *Crioprosopus servillei* Audinet-Serville, 1834. [MEX, HON]

22- *Crioprosopus thoracicus* (White, 1853). [MEX, HON]

23- *Crossomeles acutipennis* Chemsak & Noguera, 1993. [MEX, ES, NIC, CR, PAN]

24- *Curtomerus flavus* (Fabricius, 1775). [USA, MEX, ES, HON]

25- *Eburia brevicornis* Chemsak & Linsley, 1973. [MEX, BEL]

26- *Euderces aspericollis* (Chemsak, 1969). [MEX, HON]

27- *Euderces cleriformis* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, CR, PAN]

28- *Euderces cribripennis* Bates, 1892. [MEX, CR]

29- *Euderces noguerai* Giesbert & Chemsak, 1997. [MEX, BEL]

30- *Haruspex bivittis* (White, 1855). [MEX, CR, PAN]

31- *Heterachthes designatus* Martins, 1970. [MEX, HON]

32- *Ironeus mutatus* Bates, 1885. [MEX, HON]

33- *Ischnocnemis caerulea* Bates, 1885. [MEX, CR]

34- *Ischnocnemis sexualis* Bates, 1885. [MEX, CR]

35- *Limernaea ochracea* (Fisher, 1927). [MEX, CR, PAN, SA]

36- *Mallocera spinicollis* Bates, 1872. [MEX, NIC-PAN]

37- *Malobidion auricome* Chemsak & Linsley, 1963. [MEX, HON]

38- *Meganeflus fulvipennis* (Bates, 1892). [MEX, BEL]

- 39- *Mephritus apicatus* (Linsley, 1935). [MEX, NIC, CR, PAN, SA]
 40- *Methia subvittata* Chemsak & Linsley, 1964. [MEX, CR]
 41- *Micropsyrassa minima* Martins & Chemsak, 1966. [MEX, ES, HON, NIC, CR]
 42- *Mionochroma aureotinctum* (Bates, 1870). [MEX, PAN, SA]
 43- *Muscidora tricolor* Thomson 1864. [MEX, NIC, CR]
 44- *Oxymerus aculeatus lebasi* Dupont 1838. [MEX, NIC, CR, PAN, SA]
 45- *Ozodes xanthophasma* Bates, 1872. [MEX, HON, NIC, CR, PAN]
 46- *Parevander nobilis* (Bates, 1872). [MEX, NIC, CR]
 47- *Plectromerus wappesi* Giesbert, 1985. [MEX, HON]
 48- *Poeciloxestia sagittaria* (Bates, 1872). [MEX, ES, NIC, CR, SA]
 49- *Psyrassa aliena* (Linsley, 1934). [MEX, BEL]
 50- *Psyrassa androwi* Wappes, Botero & Santos-Silva, 2020. [BEL, NIC, PAN]
 51- *Psyrassa cylindricollis* Linsley, 1935. [MEX, ES]
 52- *Psyrassa nigricornis* Bates, 1892. [MEX, NIC]
 53- *Psyrassa sallaei* Bates, 1885. [USA, MEX, NIC, CR]
 54- *Smodicum clancularium* Martins, 1975. [MEX, CR]
 55- *Sphaenothecus bilineatus* (Gory in Guérin-Méneville, 1831). [USA, MEX, HON, NIC]
 56- *Sphaenothecus toledo* Chemsak & Noguera, 1998. [MEX, HON, CR]
 57- *Sphaenothecus trilineatus* Dupont, 1838. [USA, MEX, HON]
 58- *Sphallambyx mexicanus* Galileo & Martins, 2006. [MEX, CR, PAN, SA]
 59- *Stenosphenus rufipes* Bates, 1872. [MEX, NIC]
 60- *Styliceps sericatus* Pascoe, 1859. [MEX, NIC, CR, PAN, SA]
 61- *Terpnissa listropterina* Bates, 1867. [MEX, CR, PAN, SA]
 62- *Trichophoroides jansoni* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, HON, NIC, CR]
 63- *Trichoxys labyrinthicus* (Chevrolat, 1860). [MEX, HON]
 64- *Trichoxys melanotelus* (White, 1855). [MEX, NIC]
 65- *Tilloclytus balteatus* (Chevrolat, 1860) [MEX, HON, CR]
 66- *Tomopterus brevicornis* Giesbert, 1996. [MEX, NIC, CR, PAN]
 67- *Unaiuba ion* (Chevrolat, 1860). [MEX, HON, NIC, CR]
 68- *Xystochroma buprestoides* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, PAN]
 69- *Zenochloris barbicauda* Bates, 1892. [MEX, CR]

Subfamily LAMIINAE Latreille, 1825

- 70- *Adetus croton* Heffern, Santos-Silva & Botero, 2019. [USA, MEX, HON]
 71- *Adetus insularis* Breuning, 1940. [MEX, PAN]
 72- *Adetus longicauda* (Bates, 1880). [MEX, CR]
 73- *Adetus scissicauda* Bates, 1874. [MEX, NIC, PAN, SA]
 74- *Asemolea crassicornis* Bates, 1881. [MEX, BEL]
 75- *Ataxia alpha* Chemsak & Noguera, 1995. [MEX, NIC]
 76- *Ataxia canescens* (Bates, 1880). [MEX, HON]
 77- *Bebelis lignea* (Bates, 1866). [BEL, NIC, CR, PAN, SA]
 78- *Cherentes niveilateris* (Thomson, 1868). [MEX, CR, PAN, SA]
 79- *Cacostola janzeni* Chemsak & Linsley, 1986. [MEX, HON]
 80- *Colobothea aleata* Bates, 1885. [MEX, HON, NIC, CR, PAN, SA]
 81- *Colobothea chemsaki* Giesbert, 1979. [MEX, HON, CR, PAN]
 82- *Colobothea sexualis* Casey, 1913. [MEX, HON]
 83- *Corcovado bezarki* Martins & Galileo, 2008. [BEL, CR]
 84- *Cyrtinus querci* Howden, 1973. [MEX, HON]
 85- *Desmiphora orozcoi* Martins, Galileo & Santos-Silva, 2015. [BEL]
 86- *Dorcasta borealis* Breuning, 1940. [MEX, NIC]
 87- *Dorcasta parkeri* Bezark, Santos-Silva & Nascimento, 2018. [MEX, ES, NIC, CR]
 88- *Dorcasta rifkindi* Bezark, Santos-Silva & Nascimento, 2018. [MEX, PAN]
 89- *Drycothea sprete* Bates, 1885. [MEX, BEL]
 90- *Edechistatus cobosi* (Esteban & Santos-Silva, 2001). [MEX, HON]
 91- *Epectasis hiecki* Breuning, 1974. [MEX, HON]
 92- *Epectasis mexicana* Breuning, 1954. [MEX, COL]
 93- *Esthlogena (Esthlogena) nigrosuturalis* Galileo & Martins, 2011. [MEX, PAN]
 94- *Estoloides basigranulata* Breuning, 1943. [MEX, CR]

- 95- *Estoloides noguerai* Santos-Silva, Wappes & Galileo, 2018. [MEX, NIC]
 96- *Eupogonius flavocinctus* Bates, 1872. [MEX, NIC, CR]
 97- *Eupogonius piperitus* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, CR]
 98- *Eupogonius subaeneus* Bates, 1872. [MEX, HON, NIC, PAN, SA]
 99- *Eupogonius ursulus* Bates, 1872. [MEX, NIC, CR]
 100- *Eupogonius virgatus* Bezark, Botero & Santos-Silva, 2022. [MEX, CR]
 101- *Hammatoderus elatus* (Bates, 1872). [MEX, HON, NIC, CR, PAN, SA]
 102- *Hesychotypa albofasciata* Pérez-Flores & Nearn, 2021. [MEX, HON]
 103- *Lagocheirus binumeratus* Thomson, 1860. [MEX, HON, NIC, CR, PAN, SA]
 104- *Leptocometes acutispinis* (Bates, 1863). [MEX, PAN, SA]
 105- *Leptostylus aspiciens* Bates, 1885. [MEX, HON]
 106- *Leptostylus pygialis* Bates, 1872. [MEX, HON, NIC, PAN]
 107- *Lochmaeocles batesi* (Aurivillius, 1923). [MEX, HON, NIC, CR, PAN, SA]
 108- *Lochmaeocles nigratarsus* Chemsak & Linsley, 1986. [MEX, HON]
 109- *Myoxinus asper* Bates, 1880. [MEX, NIC]
 110- *Nesozineus trivialis* Galileo & Martins, 1996. [MEX, CR, PAN, SA]
 111- *Nyssodrysternum ocellatum* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, HON-PAN, SA]
 112- *Oncideres cumdisci* Noguera, 1993. [MEX, HON, NIC]
 113- *Oncideres truquii* (Thomson, 1868). [USA, MEX, NIC]
 114- *Oreodera howdeni* Monné & Fragoso, 1988. [MEX, BEL, CR, SA]
 115- *Oxathres apicofuscatus* Bezark & Santos-Silva, 2025. [BEL]
 116- *Pattalinus charis* Bates, 1881. [MEX, NIC]
 117- *Phrynidius inaequalis* (Say, 1835). [MEX, HON]
 118- *Phrynidius nayaritensis* Heffern, Nascimento & Santos-Silva, 2018. [MEX, HON]
 119- *Phaea hoegei* Bates, 1881. [MEX, HON, NIC, CR, PAN]
 120- *Phaea linsleyi* Chemsak, 1999. [MEX, NIC]
 121- *Phaea maryannae* Chemsak, 1977. [MEX, NIC]
 122- *Polymitoleiopus duffyi* (Gilmour, 1961). [MEX, NIC]
 123- *Polymitoleiopus literatus* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, HON]
 124- *Polymitoleiopus ozophagus* (Chemsak & Feller, 1988). [MEX, BEL]
 125- *Sternidius naeviicornis* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, NIC]
 126- *Tetrasarus pictulus* Bates, 1880. [MEX, HON, NIC, CR]
 127- *Thryallis sallaei* Bates, 1880. [MEX, HON]
 128- *Tucales franciscum* (Thomson, 1857). [MEX, SA]

Family DISTENIIDAE Thomson, 1860

- 1- *Elytrimitatrix hoegei* (Bates, 1885). [MEX, ES, HON, NIC, CR]
 2- *Novantinoe morrisi* Santos-Silva & Hovore, 2007. [MEX, CR]

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